

Job Satisfaction and Motivation as Predictors of Lecturers' Effectiveness in Nigeria Police Academy

Abdulkareem Hussein Bibire

Abstract—Job satisfaction and motivation have been given an important attention in psychology because they are seen as main instruments in maintaining organizational growth and development; they are also used to accomplish organizational aims and objectives. However, it has been observed that some institutions failed in motivating and stimulating their workers; in contrast, workers may be motivated but not satisfied with the job and failed to perform efficiently and effectively. It is hoped that the study of this nature would be of significance value to all stakeholders in education specifically, lecturers in higher institutions in Nigeria. Also, it is hoped that the findings of this study will enhance lecturers' effectiveness and performance in discharging their duties. In the light of the above statements, this study investigated whether job satisfaction and motivation predict lecturers' effectiveness in Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil, Kano State. Correlational research method was adopted for the study, while purposive sampling technique was used to choose the institution and the sampled lectures (70). Simple random sampling technique was used to select one hundred cadets across the academy. Two instruments were used to elicit information from both lecturers and cadets. These were job satisfaction and motivation; and lecturers' effectiveness Questionnaires. The instruments were subjected to pilot testing and found to have reliability coefficient of 0.69 and 0.71 respectively. The results of the study revealed that there was a significance relationship among job satisfaction, motivation and lecturers effectiveness in Nigeria Police Academy. There was a significance relationship between job satisfaction and lecturers' effectiveness in Nigeria Police Academy the cal r is 0.21 while the crt r is 0.19. at $p < 0.05$ and; there was a significance relationship between job motivation and lecturers effectiveness in Nigeria Police Academy the cal r is 0.20 while the crt r is 0.19 at $p < 0.05$. This study therefore concluded that there was a significance relationship among job satisfaction, motivation and lecturers effectiveness in Nigeria Police Academy. Based on the data collected, collated and analyzed Recommendations were made for both the lecturers and the Academy management. It is also suggested that lecturers should be industrious in their primary assignment in other to make values to cadets lives and career. And management should also try to enhance lecturers performance by more motivational needs for the lecturers.

Keywords—Satisfaction, motivation, lecturer effectiveness, academy.

I. INTRODUCTION

Job satisfaction has been given an important recognition in psychological realm. There are important reasons why psychologists are concerned with job satisfaction, which can be categorised based on the objective of the employee or employer (the institution). First, the humanitarian perspective

is that people deserve to be treated fairly and with respect. Job satisfaction is the reflection of a good treatment. It also can be seen as an indicator of emotional well-being or psychological health. Second, the utilitarian perspective is that job satisfaction can lead to behaviour by an employee that affects institutional growth and development. In the same vein, it can be a reflection of institutional functioning [16]. More importantly, it implies the extent to which people like their job and satisfied with it [19]. Weiss asserted that job satisfaction is an attitude which indicates to how an individual is contented with his or her job. Job satisfaction is very crucial to the long-term growth and development of any institution. It is closely predicts work effectiveness, and it has been identified that many staff lose or fail to develop work effectiveness because they were not stimulated within the institutional settings [5].

It has been established beyond doubt that various studies and researches have been carried out on reasons that could influence teachers' job satisfaction [6], [10]. Those factors include: school-specific factors like availability of material resources, lecturers-students ratio, school environment, and school culture, prompt payment of salary, and feelings of successful teaching, among others. More importantly, prompt payment of salary might be an influencing factor to the lecturers while school environment might be an influence factor to another. Job satisfaction has been demonstrated to be closely related to commitment, turnover, job effectiveness, productivity, and burnout [9].

It is generally believed that the relevance of job satisfaction and motivation are very crucial to the long-term growth of any educational system in the global village. They probably rank alongside professional knowledge and skills, center competencies, educational resources and strategies as the veritable determinants of educational success and attainment. Professional knowledge, skills, and center competencies occur when one feels effective in one's behaviour. In other words, professional knowledge, skills, effectiveness, and competencies can be seen when one is taking on and mastering challenging tasks directed at educational success and attainment [7]. In the same vein, satisfaction and motivation to work are very significant in the lives of staff because they form the fundamental reason for working in life. While almost every staff work in order to satisfy his or her needs in life, he or she constantly agitates for need satisfaction. Job satisfaction in this paper is the ability of the lecturing job to meet lecturers' needs and improve their lecturing effectiveness. Similarly, the roles and contexts of educations' motivational methods and tools cannot be underemphasized because high motivation enhances

Bibire, Abdulkareem Hussein is with the Department of Psychology, Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano State, Nigeria (e-mail: bibirehussein2013@gmail.com).

productivity which is naturally in the interests of all educational systems [13].

According to [17], motivation is a basic psychological process. Motivation is a very important element of behavior; it this is not only based on behaviour but also applicable to cognitive processes. Job motivation is described as all forms of institutional techniques applied into work system in order to meet and sustain the psychological needs of the staff and enhance their effectiveness and performance towards accomplishing and achieving the desire goals and objectives of the institution. Generally speaking, job motivation is one of the major and vital instruments of institution that have been recognized as means of achieving the institutional set objectives. It is an essential need to drive towards workable and sustainable human and non-human resources management [3]. Most of the techniques and methods adopt in stimulating institutional staff for effective work are the following: Salary, Wages and Conditions of Service; Staff Training; Information Availability and Communication; Rapid promotion as at when due; Providing job security, Staff welfare in terms of good accommodation; Creating good and harmonious relationship between school management and staff union among others [3], [17].

Reference [4] posited that there is a relationship between motivation and job satisfaction, which is paramount in any institution's existence [7]. In contrast, the concepts of motivation and job satisfaction are often confused with one another. Reference [8] demonstrated that a motivated worker is easy to spot by his or her agility, dedication, enthusiasm, focus, zeal, and general attainment and contribution to institutional objectives and goals. Researches and studies on teacher effectiveness have contributed meaningfully to the development of classroom teaching and learning and its influence on students' attainment. According to [14], an effective teacher applies systematic teaching techniques, spends enough time with students doing academic tasks, uses systematic approach with students about their academic career, runs more orderly classroom, adjusts the difficulty level of materials to students ability; have higher rate of attainment in their class room setting, and clearly articulate rules and include students in discussion about rules and procedures. According to [12], job satisfaction, job motivation, and organizational climate combined to account for 18.2% of the variance in teachers' turnover intention. Job satisfaction proved to be the most potent predictor of teacher turnover intention followed by organizational climate. In the same vein, a satisfied teacher is a stimulated teacher and vice-versa, when a teacher is satisfied with his career such individual will be motivated. Similarly, [11] posited that job satisfaction is an important factor in predicting workers effectiveness which in itself one of the factors why workers might not want to leave the institution. In contrast, job motivation was not having any potency in the prediction of teachers' turnover intention. Daramola and Agbonna stated that a significant relationships in job motivation and satisfaction among academic staff of federal and state higher institutions respectively [3]. This implies that job motivation is

a predictor of job satisfaction among academic staff of both federal and state higher institution of learning. Job motivation is one of the ways to predict job effectiveness. Again, job effectiveness is what can ensure productivity in institutional activities [1]. Job satisfaction and motivation are considered as major tools in sustaining institutional development, it is also the machinery used to achieve an institutional goals and objectives. In contrast, workers may be motivated but not satisfied with the job and affect negatively lecturers' effectiveness. In the light of the above statement, researches on job motivation and satisfaction have been carried out by various researchers on job satisfaction and motivation. It is observed from the previous studies conducted by those researchers that some gaps were left unfilled therefore this study deems it fit to fill the vacuums by examine job satisfaction and motivation as predictors of lecturers' effectiveness in Nigeria Police Academy.

II. PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of this Study was to examine job satisfaction and motivation as predictors of lecturers' effectiveness in Nigeria Police Academy.

III. HYPOTHESES

These hypotheses were formulated and tested in this study

- Ho₁: There is no significant relationship among job satisfaction, motivation, and lecturers effectiveness in Nigeria Police Academy
- Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between job satisfaction and lecturers effectiveness in Nigeria Police Academy.
- Ho₃: There is no significant relationship between job motivation, and lecturers effectiveness in Nigeria Police Academy.

IV. METHOD

This study adopted a correlational research type. It also consisted of one hundred (100) academic staff of the university (Nigeria Police Academy). Purposive sampling technique was used to select the sampled lecturers. This is in line with [18] which posited that a researcher can purposively sample respondents for use if the researcher finds any attributes of interests in the population. In addition, simple random sampling technique was used to select one hundred (100) cadets across all the departments in the academy making a total number of two hundred (200) respondents. Information was elicited through the use of an adapted questionnaire developed by [2] entitled job Satisfaction and Motivation Questionnaire (LJSMQ). This instrument consists two sections: Section A consists of the demographic data of the respondents while section B consists of seven items and section C consists of six items. The second instrument was a designed instrument on lecturers' effectiveness titled Cadet Rating Scale of Lecturers' Effectiveness (CRSLE), which was used to elicit information about lecturers' effectiveness from the selected cadets, it consists of 10 items. Both instruments

were scored on four point Likert scale on different responses Thus, (1) NS= Not Satisfied/ NW= Not Well; SS= Somewhat Satisfied/ FW=Fairly Well ATM S= Satisfied / W= Well; and VS= Very Satisfied / VW= Very Well. (2) Strongly Agree = SA, Agree = A, Strongly Disagree = SD, and Disagree = D and both were subjected to face and content validity and reliability through test re-test method using Pearson Product

Moment Correlation Coefficient Statistics (PPMC) and found to have reliability coefficient of 0.69 and 0.71 respectively.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results of data obtained from the respondents.

TABLE I
MEAN AND RANK ORDER ON JOB SATISFACTION AMONG LECTURERS IN NIGERIA POLICE ACADEMY

Item No.	I am satisfied:	Mean	Rank
7	with the regular upgrade/promotion in my job	2.77	1 st
1	with the feeling of success and security in my life brought about by my job	2.74	2 nd
4	when there is flexibility of the working hours	2.69	3 rd
3	With my current salary	2.65	4 th
6	with the communication channels used at my work place (internet, email, in-house post)	2.58	5 th
5	with the level of security at my place of work	2.52	6 th
2	with the workloads given to me in the course of my work	2.41	7 th

Table I shows that Item 7 (“I am satisfied with the regular upgrade/promotion in my job”) had the highest mean score of 2.77 and was therefore ranked 1st. Ranked 2nd was Item 1 (“I am satisfied with the feeling of success and security in my life brought about by my job”) with a mean a score of 2.74. Ranked 3rd was Item 4 (“I am satisfied when there is flexibility of the working hours”) with a mean a score of 2.69. And item 2 was ranked 7th (“I am satisfied with the workloads given to me in the course of my work”) with a mean score of 2.41. Since six out of the seven items have mean scores that are above the mid-mean score of 2.50, then it can be said that majority of the respondents affirmed to the stated items and they are also satisfied with their job in the Nigeria Police Academy.

Table II shows that Item 3 (“I am motivated jobwise when I enjoy other benefits aside from my salary”) had the highest mean score of 2.60 and was therefore ranked 1st. Ranked 2nd was Item 1 (“I am motivated jobwise when I feel that my job fulfills my basic needs”) with a mean a score of 2.58. While Ranked 5th and 6th are Items 6 and 1 (“I am motivated jobwise when I have access to motivation facilities in my institution”) and (“I am motivated jobwise when am given more work to do despite my diligence”) with mean scores of 2.48 and 2.47 respectively. Since four out of the six items have mean scores that are above the mid-mean score of 2.50, then it can be said that majority of the respondents affirmed to the stated items and they are also motivated job wise in the Nigeria Police Academy.

TABLE II
MEAN AND RANK ORDER ON JOB MOTIVATION AMONG LECTURERS IN NIGERIA POLICE ACADEMY

Item No.	I am motivated jobwise when:	Mean	Rank
3	I enjoy other benefits aside from my salary	2.60	1 st
5	I feel that my job fulfills my basic needs	2.58	2 nd
4	the condition of service soothes my chosen profession	2.57	3 rd
2	am optimistic about my future success with the institution	2.56	4 th
6	I have access to motivation facilities in my institution	2.48	5 th
1	am given more work to do despite my diligence	2.47	6 th

TABLE III
MEAN AND RANK ORDER ON LECTURERS’ EFFECTIVENESS IN NIGERIA POLICE ACADEMY

Item No.	Statement/Items	Mean	Rank
7	Lecturers are punctual in starting and ending lectures	2.72	1 st
2	Lecturers encourage students’ participation in class by questions and discussion	2.69	2 nd
10	Spend extra time with cadets who have learning difficulty	2.64	3 rd
1	Lectures are well planned and organized	2.59	4 th
8	Have thorough knowledge of subject matter with knowledge in related fields	2.57	5 th
6	Uses of variety of teaching devices, demonstrations, charts, visual aids etc	2.54	6 th
9	Have a sense of humour	2.51	7 th
3	Speak clearly and distinctly	2.48	8 th
5	Define clearly the basic for evaluating of students’ performance	2.35	9 th
4	Lecturers lack defensive attitude and prejudices	2.32	10 th

Table III shows that Item 7 (“Lecturers are punctual in starting and ending lectures”) had the highest mean score of

2.72 and was therefore ranked 1st. Ranked 2nd was Item 2 (“Lecturers encourage students’ participation in class by

questions and discussion”) with a mean a score of 2.69. Ranked third was Item 10 (“Spend extra time with cadets who have learning difficulty”) with a mean a score of 2.64. And item 4 was ranked 10th (Lecturers lack defensive attitude and prejudices) with a mean score of 2.32). Since seven out of the ten items have mean scores that are above the mid-mean score of 2.50, then it can be said that majority of the respondents affirmed to the stated items and they are also effective when it comes to discharging their duties as lecturers in the Nigeria Police Academy.

VI. HYPOTHESES TESTING

Three research hypotheses were generated and tested for this study. The hypotheses were tested using Multiple Regression Analysis and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient methods at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

- Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship among job satisfaction, motivation and lecturers effectiveness in Nigeria Police Academy.

Table IV shows a Multiple R of .242, an R square of .058 and an Adjusted R square of .039. The Multiple R of .242 represents the degree of association among measured variables. This result reveals that the two predictor variables i.e. job satisfaction and job motivation when combined did correlate significantly with lecturers’ effectiveness in Nigeria Police Academy. The Multiple R was tested for significance with an F-ratio statistics. The result of the ANOVA, Table V, indicates an F-value of $F(3, 97) = 3.01, p < 0.05$. This further implies that the correlation between the predictors and outcome variables is statistically significant. Table V further expressed the result of the relative contribution of job satisfaction and job motivation as correlates of lecturers’ effectiveness in Nigeria Police Academy. Job satisfaction had a Beta weight (β) of .125, $t = 3.253, p < 0.05$, Job motivation had a Beta weight (β) of .185, $t = 3.849, p < 0.05$. Therefore, hypothesis 1 which states that there is no significant relationship among job satisfaction, motivation and lecturers’ effectiveness in Nigeria Police Academy is hereby rejected.

- Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between job satisfaction and lecturers’ effectiveness in Nigeria Police Academy.

The result in Table VII indicated that the calculated r is 0.21 while the critical r is 0.19. Since the calculated r is greater than the critical r , there is a significant relationship. Hence, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between job satisfaction and lecturers’ effectiveness in Nigeria Police Academy is rejected.

- Hypothesis Three: There is no significant relationship between job motivation and lecturers’ effectiveness in Nigeria Police Academy

The result in Table VIII indicated that the calculated r is 0.20 while the critical r is 0.19. Since the calculated r is greater than the critical r , there is a significant relationship. Hence, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between job motivation and lecturers’ effectiveness in Nigeria Police Academy is rejected.

TABLE IV
SUMMARY TABLE OF MULTIPLE REGRESSION ANALYSIS OF JOB SATISFACTION, MOTIVATION, AND LECTURERS EFFECTIVENESS IN NIGERIA POLICE ACADEMY MODEL SUMMARY

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.242	.058	.039	4.348

TABLE V
ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	113.929	2	56.96	3.01*	.05
Residual	1834.431	97	18.91		
Total	1948.360	99			

TABLE VI
REGRESSION ANALYSIS SHOWING JOB SATISFACTION AND MOTIVATION AS CORRELATES OF LECTURERS EFFECTIVENESS IN NIGERIA POLICE ACADEMY

Model	B	Std. Error	Beta	Calculated t-value	Sig.
Constant	20.172	3.036		6.645	.000
Job Satisfaction	.156	.125	.125	3.253*	.012
Job Motivation	.254	.137	.185	3.849*	.019

TABLE VII
CORRELATION BETWEEN JOB SATISFACTION AND LECTURERS’ EFFECTIVENESS IN NIGERIA POLICE ACADEMY

Correlation	Mean	SD	df	Cal. R	Crit. R
Job Satisfaction	19.24	3.56	98	0.21*	0.19
Lecturers’ Effectiveness	27.42	4.43			

*Significant, $p < 0.05$

TABLE VIII
CORRELATION BETWEEN JOB MOTIVATION AND LECTURERS’ EFFECTIVENESS IN NIGERIA POLICE ACADEMY

Correlation	Mean	SD	df	Cal. R	Crit. R
Job Motivation	16.72	3.23	98	0.20*	0.19
Lecturers’ Effectiveness	27.42	4.43			

*Significant, $p < 0.05$

VII. DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The findings of this study revealed that there was a significant relationship among job satisfaction, motivation, and lecturers’ effectiveness in Nigeria Police Academy. This finding is in line with the finding of [12] who posited that job satisfaction, job motivation, and organizational climate combined to account for 18.2% of the variance in teachers’ turnover intention. Job satisfaction proved to be the most potent predictor of teacher effectiveness. In the same vein, a satisfied teacher is a stimulated teacher and vice-versa, when a teacher is satisfied with his career such individual will be motivated. Similarly, the findings is corroborated with the result of [11] posited that job satisfaction is an important factor in predicting workers effectiveness which in itself one of the factors why workers might not want to leave the institution. In contrast, job motivation was not having any potency in the prediction of teachers’ turnover intention [12].

The findings of this study also revealed that there was a significant relationship between job satisfaction and lecturers effectiveness in Nigeria Police Academy and there was a significance relationship between job motivation and lecturers effectiveness in Nigeria Police Academy. The findings

corroborated with the findings of [3] there was significant relationships in job motivation and satisfaction among academic staff of federal and state higher institutions respectively. This implies that job motivation is a predictor of job satisfaction among academic staff of both federal and state higher institution of learning. More importantly, they quoted that two factor theory of job motivation postulated that job motivation has a particular function of arousing job satisfaction this indicates that job satisfaction itself leads to effectiveness of teachers. According [3] job motivation is a way of predicting job effectiveness. Again, job effectiveness is what can ensure productivity in institutional activities [1]. Against this study, the study of [12] posited that job motivation and job satisfaction accounted for low variance labour turnover which also be related to job effectiveness.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Based on the data generated and the hypotheses tested the results of the findings revealed that there was a significance relationship among job satisfaction, motivation and lecturers' effectiveness, there was a significance relationship between job satisfaction and lecturers effectiveness and there was a significance relationship between job motivation and lecturers effectiveness in Nigeria Police Academy

IX. RECOMMENDATIONS

In view of the findings of this study, the paper recommends that:

- 1) Lecturers should be more pro-active and more effective in their primary assignment (teaching) in order to make meaningful impacts and inputs in the life of cadets and boost the standard of the academy.
- 2) In the same vein, it is recommends that management should intensify efforts to improve lecturers' welfares by providing more motivational techniques to enhance more productivity.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. A. Agbona, Influence of normative and participatory administrative strategies in secondary school teachers commitment to duties in Kwara State. University of Ilorin, (Unpublished Ph. D thesis, University of Ilorin, Nigeria) 2009.
- [2] S Anna, & S. Sanni, Employee satisfaction and work motivation. A published project submitted to the Mikkali University of Applied Sciences.2010.
- [3] C. O. Daramola, & S. A. Agbonna, Job Motivation as Correlate of Job Satisfaction among Academic Staff of Higher Institutions in Kwara State, Nigeria. *Journal of Research in Education* 2011 (1), P 36-41.
- [4] G. Dessler, Management: Leading People and Organization in the 21st Century. Harlow: Prentice Hall. 2001.
- [5] C. S. Dweck, *Self-theories: Their role in Motivation, Personality, and Development*. Philadelphia, PA: Psychology Press, 1999.
- [6] XEvans, Teacher morale, job satisfaction and motivation. London: Paul Chapman Publishing Ltd., 1998
- [7] V. F Filak, & K. M. Sheldon, Student Psychological Need Satisfaction and College Teacher-Course Evaluations. *Educational Psychology*, (2003)23, (3), P 235-247.
- [8] P. Ifinedo, Employee Motivation and Job Satisfaction in Finnish Organizations: A Study of Employees in the Oulu Region, Finland. Master of Business Administration Thesis, University of London, 2003
- [9] A. Khaleque; M. M. Hossain; & M. E. Hoque, Job satisfaction, fatigue and performance of industrial workers. *Psychological Studies*, (1992). J 37, p 136—141.
- [10] M. Mäenpää, Teachers of English in Finnish upper secondary general school and their job satisfaction. Pro Gradu Thesis. University of Jyväskylä, Department of Languages.2005
- [11] J. P; Mayers, S. V. Pavinomen; Gallatly, I. R; Goffin, R. D & Jackson, D. N (1989).Organizational commitment and job performance. Its nature of the commitment that counts. *Journal of applied psychology* 74, 152-156.
- [12] A. O. Ogunbanjo, Job satisfaction, job motivation and organizational climate as determinants of teachers turnover intention: Implication for Mental Health. *Journal of the Nigeria Society of educational psychologists* 2010, 8, P 49-55.
- [13] N. P. Ololube. Professionalism: An Institutional Approach to Teachers' Job Effectiveness in Nigerian Schools. Paper Presented at the Seventh International LL in E Conference, 2004.
- [14] B. A. Omotosho, I. O. Olayinwola; & O. Onadiji, Teachers' Effectiveness in maintaining standards in Private Schools. *Nigeria Journal of Educational Research and Evaluation*, 201211, (2), P 1-12.
- [15] Onabanjo, Commitment of teaching through proper training. *Teachers' journal* 20051, P 14.
- [16] P. E. Spector, Job satisfaction: application, assessment, cause, and consequences. USA. SAGE Publications, Inc., 1997.
- [17] A. Tella, C. O. Ayeni, & S. O. Popoola, Working motivation, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment of Library personnel in academic and research libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Library philosophy and practice*, 2007
- [18] A. A. Ujo, Social research: a non-quantitative approach. Nigeria: Anyaotu Enterprise and publisher Ltd.2000.
- [19] H. M. Weiss, De-constructing job satisfaction: Separating evaluations, beliefs and affective experiences. *Human Resources Management Review*, 2002 12, P173-194.